

European network to promote grazing and to support grazing-based farms on their economic and ecologic performances as well as on animal welfare

Project Acronym: **Grazing4AgroEcology**
Project Number: 101059626

Deliverable No.: D6.5
Deliverable Title: 1st Self-assessment tool of sustainability of grazing-based farms and associated results as a result of Task 6.2

Responsible Partner: Grünlandzentrum
Niedersachsen/Bremen e.V.

Due date: 31 Oct 2023
Submission Date: 31 Oct 2023
Dissemination level: PU

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101059626	42 Months	September 2022

Contributors

Name

Arno Krause

Organisation

Grünlandzentrum Niedersachsen/Bremen
e.V.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101059626. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Index of Contents

1	Inventory and assessment of relevant tools	4
1.1	Assigning inventoried tools to agroecological pillars	4
1.2	Evaluation of tools.....	4
1.3	Further exploitation of the tool inventory	5
2	Development of the G4AE self-assessment tool.....	7
2.1	Transfer from T2.2 to T6.2	7
2.2	Functionality.....	7
3	References.....	10
4	Appendix.....	11
4.1	Inventory of tools	11
4.1.1	Assignments of tools to the five agroecological pillars.....	11
4.1.2	Evaluation of tools by countries	15
4.2	Self-assessment tool.....	27
4.2.1	Questions Pillar “Reducing Inputs”	27
4.2.2	Questions Pillar “Enhancing Diversity”	32
4.2.3	Questions Pillar “Reducing Pollution”	36
4.2.4	Questions Pillar “Biodiversity”	40
4.2.5	Questions Pillar “Animal Welfare”	47
4.2.6	Radar graph summarising results of each pillar	50
4.2.7	Dropdown values.....	51

1 Inventory and assessment of relevant tools

Due to different agroecological and socioeconomic conditions in each partner country, a form was generated to survey all relevant tools available for agricultural advisors and farmers in the grazing context per country and to take these regional contexts into account. A review of the available tools revealed a significant diversity of thematic areas and fields of application.

1.1 Assigning inventoried tools to agroecological pillars

Each tool was assigned to one or multiple pillars of agroecology following the classification developed by Dumont et al. (2013) which is also referenced in the proposal (p. 4).

1. adopting management practices that aim to improve animal health
2. reducing the inputs required for production
3. reducing pollution by optimising the biogeochemical functioning of farming systems
4. enhancing diversity within animal production systems to strengthen their resilience
5. preserving biodiversity in agro-ecosystems by adapting management practices

The form captures these 5 principles (Fig. 1), including other key facts such as property rights, URL and the national origin of the respective tool.

Name of Tool	Aspect					Licensing	URL	Edited by (please attach national code after inserting or editing)	Comments
	Animal Welfare	Input Reduction	Soil Health	Diversity of Animal Production Systems	Agro-biodiversity Practices				

Figure 1: Form to assign each inventoried tool to agroecological pillars/aspects (shaded yellow).

The results are shown in [-> Appendix 4.1.1](#).

1.2 Evaluation of tools

In a second step, the characteristics of each tool were evaluated. This selection of criteria loosely followed the set of criteria given in the FAIRshare assessment tool (<https://fairshare-pnf.eu/assessment-tool>, accessed on: 18 October 2023). Thus, in a separate sheet, each tool was assessed by the 27 criteria. These criteria were grouped into 4 major categories (Fig. 2):

1. Usability
2. Data Management
3. Scope
4. Knowledge exchange

National Code: DE		RISE	
Category	Criterion	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
	Target Group	other (see "Comments")	all
Usability	Complexity	3	
	Provides user interface in English	1	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")	1	DK, DE, EN, ES, PT, FR, TR, ID
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter	0 1	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing	2	
	Offline functionality	1	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)	Windows	
	Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)	Independent (web-based)	Optimized for MS Internet Explorer
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production	3	
	Input data is checked	2	
	Supports data imports/exports	2	Can produce Excel/Word-Reports
	Management of individual profile data	4	
	Ensures data security/privacy	4	

Figure 2: Screenshot of the 27 evaluation criteria form, grouped into 4 categories (shown here: Criteria of the categories "Usability" and "Data Management" in the evaluation of the RISE tool by German partners).

The criteria were assessed through

- binary answer options: "0" – "No", "1" – "Yes" or
- scored on a numeric scale where "1" ranks as "Very low", "4" ranks as "Very high"

This way, a generic inventory form was created which was applicable for all European partners in their respective contexts and at the same time ensured comparability for the creation of a common understanding of the tools' characteristics.

In total, 8 national inventories, each consisting of 2 sheets (cf. Fig. 1, 2) were made and the data subsequently synthesised and compiled to 1 inventory file -> [Appendix 4.1.2](#). All countries except Sweden and Italy submitted a full inventory including the evaluation of criteria.

1.3 Further exploitation of the tool inventory

The inventory was submitted to the STWG to agree on the exploitation of the inventory in the further development of the self-assessment tool. Two limitations were identified from the inventory: First, the overall wide variety of technical functionalities limits the European-wide application of each tool in the field. Second, no tool addresses all relevant thematic areas of each agroecological pillar. Therefore, it was agreed to build a separate Grazing4AgroEcology-tool which provides an optimum outcome in terms of the categories of criteria from -> [1.2](#).

In summary, these criteria were incorporated into the tool creation as a) being intuitive and easy to use, b) being free of cost, c) providing concise and specific results both in a quantitative and qualitative way and c) providing illustrative, visual results easy to be comprehended by farmers.

2 Development of the G4AE self-assessment tool

2.1 Transfer from T2.2 to T6.2

As determined during the Steering Committee meeting on 5 June 2023, the STWG had split up into three sub-groups to discuss and revise an extensive list of indicators from T2.2 (*D2.2 List of indicators for self-assessment as result of Task 2.2*) which were decided to provide the basis for the self-assessment tool. The sub-groups were formed ensuring that each had a diverse composition of professional expertise on specific subjects and agro-climatic zones. This approach ensured that the indicators address each pillar from a pan-European perspective and are equally applicable in each regional European grazing context. The three sub-groups met during the 3rd GPA in Rennes again in person to finalise the remaining indicators with regard to their usability in the tool. The total number of indicators and thus questions in the tool amount to 129:

Reducing Inputs	35
Enhancing Diversity	22
Reducing Pollution	24
Biodiversity	28
Animal Welfare	20

2.2 Functionality

The assessment of 129 questions results in five different results, one for each pillar. Results range on a percentage scale from 0-100 %, where low values express rather poor and high values rather high farm performance.

The tool is accessible as one Microsoft Excel file and subdivided into seven sheets, five of which consist of the self-assessment questions of the five agroecological pillars ([-> 1.1](#)). Another sheet is functionally linked to these five sheets and provides a quantitative and graphical output of the self-assessment, thus providing an intuitive basis for discussion between advisors and farmers. The last sheet contains meta data for the formulas. The interface language is currently in English and will be translated into all other member state languages. The structure of each self-assessment sheet is listed in [-> Appendix 4.2](#):

- Column A: consecutive numbering
- Column B: Agroecological pillar (synonymous with sheet titles “*Reducing Inputs*”, “*Enhancing Diversity*”, “*Reducing Pollution*”, “*Biodiversity*”, “*Animal Welfare*”
- Column C, D: Sub-pillars and categories allow a further grouping of questions and therefore a more fine-grained result of the farm performance in sub-thematic areas.
- Column E, F: Each question is assigned to a weight, that is, the relative importance to other questions. Weights range from 0-1 where 1 is the highest possible value of importance and 0.1 equals to least importance. 0 is “*not applicable*” and means that this question is taken out altogether of the assessment. These columns are therefore closely linked to the answer options of column I. They are part of the meta data section and are thus neither editable nor visible in the user interface
- Column G: Question

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Nr.	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Weight (default: 1)	Effective Weight (0 for n.a.)	Question
1	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Legumes	1	1	Do you have legumes in your grasslands?
2	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Legumes	1	1	Do you put legumes in your grasslands available for sow?
3	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Legumes	1	1	What is the maximum proportion of legumes in you pastures throughout the year?
4	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Sufficient forage production	1	1	What percentage of forage used is produced on your farm in the last three years?
5	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Grassland Management	1	1	If you mow your grasslands, is your post mowing height for silage/hay between 6 - 8 cm ?
6	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Grassland Management	1	1	What is the proportion from the optimal grazing period that your animals spend grazing a year?
7	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage	Spring grazing	1	0	Do you try to graze as early as possible in spring?

Figure 3: Screenshot of column A-G from the sheet of pillar “Reducing Inputs”. Columns shaded yellow are the user interface; white columns are hidden.

- Column H: The field type assigns the answer options of column I to classes
- Column I: Answer options (“Field value”) are provided in a drop-down list. Each qualitative or quantitative answer option results to an unique value of goodness in column J, except of the answer option “n.a.” (not applicable). If a question cannot be reasonably answered, opting for “n.a.” resets the weight of this question to 0 in column F and does not contribute to the quantitative result of the assessment.
- Column J: The eval/use value provides the value of goodness depending on which answer option was selected in column I. Values are given in percentage and range from 0-100, where 0 yields no contribution to the overall result and 100 yields the best possible result.
- Column K, L: Each sheet and pillar provide a distinct, quantitative result (“Eval Result (%)”) as a sum product of the weighted (column F) eval values (column J); the formula of the result value is therefore:

$$=SUMPRODUCT(J:J;F:F)/SUM(F:F)$$

H	I	J	K	L
Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	34,7
yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100,0		
yes_positive_0_100_na	Yes	100,0		
perc_legumes	<10%	25,0		
perc_farmforage	All (100%)	100,0		
yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0,0		
grazing_days	< 40%	0,0		
yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		

Figure 4: Screenshot of column H-L from the sheet of pillar “Reducing Inputs”.

- Sheet Radar Graph: Provides a graphical output of the five different evaluation results from the L-columns of each pillar sheet in a radar graph (Figure 3). In addition, pillar-specific radar graphs (resulting from the sub-pillars) are created, thus plotting another five radar graphs.

Figure 5: Exemplary result of the imaginary self-assessment of a farm would rank rather low in Reducing Inputs (34,4 %), Animal Welfare (37 %), Enhancing Diversity (27,3 %), medium in Reducing Pollution (57 %) and rather well in Biodiversity (71,3 %).

The tool is a synthesis from a Europe-wide inventory of existing tools, the determination of indicators for optimum grazing capacities on farm level and, finally, adjustment and fine-tuning by profound scientific expertise from across all member states. We are confident that this tool is critical for the future work of advisors, extension officers and practitioners alike for substantiated and usable assessments of European farms who are striving to improve their agroecological orientation.

It is available to the public and can be accessed on the Grazing4AgroEcology website:
<https://grazing4agroecology.eu/innovations/infothek-publikationen/>

3 References

Dumont, B., et al., 2013. Prospects from agroecology and industrial ecology for animal production in the 21st century. *Animal*, 7(6)

4 Appendix

4.1 Inventory of tools

4.1.1 Assignments of tools to the five agroecological pillars

Name of Tool	Pillar					Licensing	URLs	Edited by	Comments
	Animal Welfare	Input Reduction	Soil Health	Diversity of Animal Production Systems	Agro-biodiversity Practices				
AGRO BI		•		•		Restricted (specified in "Comments")	https://sway.office.com/bMxE4KZPnV6b8axq?ref=Link	PT	Paid software
Agroecological Risk and Resilience Screening Tool	•	•	•	•	•	Unknown	https://fsnnetwork.org/resource/agroecological-risk-and-resilience-screening-tool	IT	
Agroecology Info Pool - criteria tool	•	•	•	•	•	Unknown	https://www.agroecology-pool.org/methodology/	IT	
Autosysel - Feed self-sufficiency		•		•	•	Free & Open	https://idele.fr/autosysel	FR	
Benchmark	•			•		Unknown	http://46.101.232.35:3838/dec_tool/	DE	Prototype
Biodiversiteitsmonitor		•		•	•		https://biodiversiteitsmonitor.nl/	NL	
Biodiversity Planning – Wildlife Assessment Check					•	Unknown	https://www.biodiversityinplanning.org/wildlife-assessment-check/	IT	
BIOTEX (Units : Permanent grassland and Soil fertility4.0)		•	•		•	Free & Open	https://idele.fr/detail-article/biotex-une-demarche-devaluation-multicritere-de-la-biodiversite-ordinaire-dans-les-systemes-dexploitation-delevage-et-de-polyculture-elevage	FR	New version BIOTEX4,0 including soil health

Bride Project Score Cards		•		•	•	Free & Open	https://www.thebrideproject.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/BRIDE-Project-Habitat-Score-Cards.pdf	IE	
Classyfarm	•					Unknown	https://classyfarm.it	IT	
Cool farm Tool: Biodiversity assessment					•	Unknown	https://app.coolfarmtool.org/biodiversity/assessment/	IT	
Devautop - Protein self-sufficiency		•				Restricted (specified in "Comments")	https://idele.fr/detail-article/devautop	FR	License
ESSIMAGE	•	•	•	•	•	Unknown	no homepage was found	IT	
EU Biodiversity Performance Tool					•	Unknown	https://bpt.biodiversity-performance.eu/	IT	
Fairshare - DATS Assessment Tool	•	•	•	•	•	Free & Open	https://fairshare-pnf.eu/assessment-tool	PT	
Farm Sustainability Assessment		•			•	Unknown	https://saipatform.org/fsa/	Unknow	Introduction: https://youtu.be/vLO2qDS6hWE
Graslandkompas		•	•			Restricted (specified in "Comments")		NL	Available for developers (Aeres is one of them)
Grass10 Grazing Checklist		•		•	•	Free & Open	N/A (available via Michael O'Donovan)	IE	Michael.odonovan@teagasc.ie
Greppa näringen		•	•		•	Free & Open	https://greppa.nu	SE	An extension tool having been developed over more than 20 years. Started with nutrient balances, but has been developed with a module for climate check and biodiversity. Has been used by a vast number of farmers. Administrated by the Swedish Board of Agriculture. In Swedish only.

Grofvoderverktyget - Grovfoderkalkylen		•				Restricted (specified in "Comments")	http://grofvoderverktyget.se/?p=31069&m=4479	SE	A fee for user. In Swedish only.
Kringloopwijzer		•				Free & Open	https://mijnkringloopwijzer.nl/	NL	
LIFE MIL'OUV					•	Unknown	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/index.cfm?fuseaction=search	IT	
Oppla – Biodiversity Planning Toolkit					•	Unknown	https://oppla.eu/product/1928	IT	
PastureBase Ireland		•				Restricted (specified in "Comments")	https://pasturebase.teagasc.ie/	IE	need to register
Public Goods Tool (PG-Tool SustainFARM)	•	•	•	•	•	Free & Open	http://www.sustainfarm.eu/en/decision-support-tool/ ; https://www.organicresearchcentre.com/our-research/research-project-library/public-goods-tool/	IT;DE;RO;SE	Identical to SustainFARM PG tool, ORC is the original source; The tool is modified continuously. At present there are more recent versions also including e.g. economics and social well-being. The url link is just an example of how it can look like in a specific project.
RISE	•	•	•	•	•	Restricted (specified in "Comments")	https://www.bfh.ch/de/forschung/alle-dienstleistungen/rise/	DE	Manual only for Version 3.0(2015!) from Costs for license and support; Nestlé is involved
SAFA Tool 2.2.40	•	•	•	•	•	Free & Open	https://www.fao.org/nr/sustainability/sustainability-assessments-safa/safa-tool/en/	DE	Not suitable for intended target groups (SF, PL)
Simulatiestool eco-activiteiten		•	•	•	•	Free & Open	https://www.rvo.nl/onderwerpen/eco-regeling/simulatiestool	NL	
SMART - Sustainability Monitoring and	•	•	•	•	•	Unknown	https://www.fibl.org/en/themes/smart-en/	IT	

Assessment RouTine									
TAPE - Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation	•	•	•	•	•	Unknown	https://www.fao.org/agroecology/tools-tape/en/	IT	
Teagasc DairyMIS Score Card	•	•		•	•	Free & Open	N/A (available via Michael O'Donovan)	IE	Michael.odonovan@teagasc.ie
TEKla		•				Free & Open	NA (available via Geman Agricultural Chamber)	DE	
The agroecological diagnosis	•	•	•	•	•	Free & Open	https://www.diagagroeco.org/	FR	
Weiderechner	•			•		Free & Open	http://46.101.232.35:3838/DMI_app/	DE	Prototype
Welfare Quality© Assesmet Protocols	•					Free & Open	http://www.welfarequalitynetwork.net/en-us/reports/assessment-protocols	NL	

4.1.2 Evaluation of tools by countries

	National Code: DE		RISE		TEKLa		
Category	Criterion		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises		4	see manual page 35		3	
	Increases farm profitability		2			3	
	Reduction of input use		1			1	
	Assesses animal welfare		1			0	
	Improves animal welfare		1			0	
	Assesses biodiversity		1			0	
	Improves biodiversity		1			0	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures		2			3	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures		3			1	
	Is generally applicable in any European region		4		Was applied worldwide (4500 farms in 62 nations, see doc)		2
Knowledge exchange	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange		3			3	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)		4			3	
	Unveils implicit knowledge		4			1	

	National Code: FR	<i>The agroecological diagnosis</i>		<i>BIOTEX (Units : Permanent grassland and Soil fertility4.0)</i>		<i>Autosysel</i>		<i>Devautop</i>	
Category	Criterion	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
	Target Group	Farmer + Adviser		Farmer + Adviser		Farmer + Adviser		Farmer + Adviser	
Usability	Complexity	2		2		1		2	
	Provides user interface in English	0		1		0		0	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")	0		0		0		0	
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter	3		3		4		3	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing	3		4		3		3	
	Offline functionality	0		0		0		0	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)	Independent (web-based)		Windows		Independent (web-based)		Independent (web-based)	
Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)	Independent (web-based)		Independent (web-based)		Independent (web-based)		Independent (web-based)		
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production	2		3		2		3	
	Input data is checked	1		3		1		3	
	Supports data imports/exports	1		3		1		3	
	Management of individual profile data	4		4		4		4	
	Ensures data security/privacy	4		4		4		4	

	National Code: FR	<i>The agroecological diagnosis</i>		<i>BIOTEX (Units : Permanent grassland and Soil fertility4.0)</i>		<i>Autosysel</i>		<i>Devautop</i>	
Category	Criterion	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises	3		3		1		4	
	Increases farm profitability	3		4		3		3	
	Reduction of input use	1		1		1		1	
	Assesses animal welfare	1		0		0		0	
	Improves animal welfare	0		0		0		0	
	Assesses biodiversity	1		1		0		0	
	Improves biodiversity	1		1		0		0	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures	3		2		3		0	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures	3		2		4		0	
	Is generally applicable in any European region	3		3		4		3	
Knowledge exchange	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange	3		3		4		3	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)	3		3		4		3	
	Unveils implicit knowledge	3		3		4		3	

	National Code: IE	PastureBase Ireland		Bride Project Score Cards		Teagasc DairyMIS Score Card		Grass10 Grazing Checklist	
Category	Criterion	Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments						
	Target Group	Farmer + Adviser							
Usability	Complexity	2		2		1		1	
	Provides user interface in English	1		1		1		1	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")	0		0		0		0	
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter	1		1		2		1	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing	0		1		1		1	
	Offline functionality	1		1		1		1	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)	Windows					Windows		Windows
Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)	all OS & web								
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production	2		0		3		1	
	Input data is checked	2		0		1		0	
	Supports data imports/exports	2		0		2		1	
	Management of individual profile data	2		0		4		3	
	Ensures data security/privacy	3		0		3		3	
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises	0		0		3		1	
	Increases farm profitability	3		1		3		3	
	Reduction of input use	1		1		1		1	
	Assesses animal welfare	0		0		1		0	
	Improves animal welfare	0		0		1		0	
	Assesses biodiversity	0		1		1		0	
	Improves biodiversity	0		1		1		0	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures	2		0		1		0	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures	2		1		1		0	
Is generally applicable in any European region	2		1		1		3		
Knowledge exchange	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange	4		2		3		4	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)	4		1		3		4	
	Unveils implicit knowledge	2		2		2		1	

	National Code: NL		Graslandkompas			Kringloopwijzer			Simulatietool eco-activiteiten	
Category	Criterion		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
	Target Group		Farmer + Adviser			Farmer + Adviser			Farmer + Adviser	
Usability	Complexity		2			4			1	
	Provides user interface in English		0			0			0	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")		1	NL		1	NL		1	NL
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter		2			4			1	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing		3			3			4	
	Offline functionality		1			1	However, always used online		0	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)		all OS & web			all OS & web			all OS & web	
	Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)		all OS & web			all OS & web			all OS & web	
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production		3			4			2	
	Input data is checked		2			4			3	
	Supports data imports/exports		1			4			3	
	Management of individual profile data		0			4			1	
	Ensures data security/privacy		2			4			4	
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises		3			2			2	
	Increases farm profitability		4			1			2	
	Reduction of input use		1			1			1	
	Assesses animal welfare		0			0			0	
	Improves animal welfare		0			0			0	
	Assesses biodiversity		0			0			1	
	Improves biodiversity		0			0			1	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures		0			2			2	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures		0			1			3	
Is generally applicable in any European region		2			1			2		
Knowledge	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange		4			4			1	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)		4			4			1	

	Unveils implicit knowledge		4				4					1		
--	----------------------------	--	---	--	--	--	---	--	--	--	--	---	--	--

	National Code: NL		Biodiversiteitsmonitor			Public Goods Tool			Welfare Quality ©	
Category	Criterion		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
	Target Group		other (see "Comments")	all stakeholders		Researcher			Policy Maker + Researcher	
Usability	Complexity		2			4			4	
	Provides user interface in English		0			1			1	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")		1	NL		0			0	
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter		2			4			4	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing		3			4			3	
	Offline functionality		0			1			1	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)		Independent (web-based)			Independent (web-based)			Independent (web-based)	
	Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)		Independent (web-based)			Independent (web-based)			Independent (web-based)	
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production		3			3			3	
	Input data is checked		2			2			2	
	Supports data imports/exports		2			0			1	
	Management of individual profile data		2			2			2	
	Ensures data security/privacy		2			3			2	
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises		0			0			0	
	Increases farm profitability		0			0			0	
	Reduction of input use		1			1			0	
	Assesses animal welfare		0			1			1	
	Improves animal welfare		0			1			1	
	Assesses biodiversity		1			1			0	
	Improves biodiversity		1			1			0	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures		1			2			0	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures		1			2			0	
Is generally applicable in any European region		1			4			4		
Knowledge	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange		2			2			2	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)		2			2			2	

	Unveils implicit knowledge		2				3			3		
--	----------------------------	--	---	--	--	--	---	--	--	---	--	--

	National Code: PT		Fairshare - DATS Assessment Tool			AGRO BI			Farm Sustainability Assessment	
Category	Criterion		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
	Target Group		Adviser			Farmer + Adviser			other (see "Comments")	Company + famers (Food supply chain)
Usability	Complexity		2			3			2	
	Provides user interface in English		1			1			1	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")		1	HR, NL, FR, DE, GR, HU, LT, PT, SL, ES		1	PT		1	21 Languages
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter		2			3			2	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing		2			0			0	
	Offline functionality		1			1			0	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)		Windows			Windows			all OS & web	
	Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)		all OS & web			all OS & web			all OS & web	
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production		2			3			3	
	Input data is checked		2			3			4	
	Supports data imports/exports		3			3			4	
	Management of individual profile data		3			3			4	
	Ensures data security/privacy		3			2			3	
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises		0			3			0	
	Increases farm profitability		2			3			1	
	Reduction of input use		1			1			0	
	Assesses animal welfare		0			0			0	
	Improves animal welfare		0			0			0	
	Assesses biodiversity		0			0			0	
	Improves biodiversity		0			0			0	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures		2			0			0	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures		2			0			0	
Is generally applicable in any European region		4			4			4		
Knowledge	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange		3			3			3	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)		3			3			2	

	Unveils implicit knowledge		3				3		
--	----------------------------	--	---	--	--	--	---	--	--

	National Code: RO		PG-Tool	
Category	Criterion		Degree of fulfilment /Value	Comments
	Target Group		Researcher	
Usability	Complexity		3	
	Provides user interface in English		1	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")		0	
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter		3	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing		3	
	Offline functionality		1	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)		Windows/macOS	
	Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)			Not sure it can be used from mobile
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production		3	
	Input data is checked		0	
	Supports data imports/exports		0	
	Management of individual profile data		3	
	Ensures data security/privacy		3	
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises		3	
	Increases farm profitability		3	
	Reduction of input use		0	
	Assesses animal welfare		1	
	Improves animal welfare		0	
	Assesses biodiversity		1	
	Improves biodiversity		0	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures		0	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures		0	
	Is generally applicable in any European region		3	
Knowledge exchange	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange		3	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)		3	
	Unveils implicit knowledge		2	

	National Code: SE		Public Goods Tool	
Category	Criterion		Degree of fulfilment / Value	Comments
	Target Group		Farmer + Adviser	
Usability	Complexity		3	
	Provides user interface in English		1	
	Provides other user interface languages than English (write these into field "Comments")		0	
	The information is organized in a way that supports deep understanding of the complexity of the subject matter		2	
	Transparency according to the methods of data processing		4	
	Offline functionality		1	
	Desktop: supported platforms (Windows, macOS, Linux, web)		Windows/macOS/Linux	Excel
	Mobile: supported platforms (iOS, Android, web)		iOS/Android	Excel
Data Management	Quantitative acquisition and evaluation of significant parameters of production		4	
	Input data is checked		4	
	Supports data imports/exports		0	
	Management of individual profile data		4	
	Ensures data security/privacy		4	
Scope	Facilitates economical evaluation and comparison of agricultural enterprises		4	
	Increases farm profitability		2	
	Reduction of input use		1	
	Assesses animal welfare		1	
	Improves animal welfare		1	
	Assesses biodiversity		1	
	Improves biodiversity		1	
	Meets climate change mitigation measures		2	
	Meets climate change adaptation & resilience measures		3	
	Is generally applicable in any European region		4	
Knowledge exchange	Facilitates peer-to-peer exchange		4	
	Facilitates exchange between different target groups (e.g. farmer <-> advisor)		4	
	Unveils implicit knowledge		3	

4.2 Self-assessment tool

4.2.1 Questions Pillar “Reducing Inputs”

Nr.	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Weight (default: 1)	Effective Weight (0 for n.a.)	Question	Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	27,4
1	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	1	1	Do you have legumes in your grasslands?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
2	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	1	1	Do you put legumes in your grasslands available for sow?	yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0,0		
3	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	1	1	What is the maximum proportion of legumes in you pastures throughout the year?	perc_legumes	<10%	25,0		
4	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Sufficient forage production	1	1	What percentage of forage used is produced on your farm in the last three years?	perc_farmforage	All (100%)	100,0		
5	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Grassland Management	1	1	If you mow your grasslands, is your post mowing height for silage/hay between 6 - 8 cm ?	yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0,0		
6	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Grassland Management	1	1	What is the proportion from the optimal grazing period that your animals spend grazing a year?	grazing_days	< 40%	0,0		

7	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	0	Do you try to graze as early as possible in spring?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
8	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	When animals are grazing in the spring are they fed additional forage (hay, silage, haylage, maize silage etc)?	yes_positive_50_100	Yes	50,0		
9	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	If animals are given additional forage in the best grazing period during a year what % of their diet is it?	perc_springdiet	> 20%	0,0		
10	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	During the best yearly grazing period, how much concentrate do you feed a day to a mother animal?	kg_concentrate_spring	>3 kg/cow; > 0,5 kg /small ruminants	25,0		
11	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	If you do feed concentrate during the best yearly grazing period what crude protein percentage is it?	perc_XP	< 15%	100,0		
12	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Summer grazing	1	1	During summer, how much of the day are animals on pastures?	hours_grazing	No grazing	0,0		
13	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Summer grazing	1	1	During summer, how much concentrate do you feed a day to a mother animal?	kg_concentrate_summer	0 kg/animal	100,0		
14	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Autumn grazing	1	1	In autumn, how much of the day are animals on pastures?	autumn_grazing	Not on pasture	0,0		

15	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	1	1	What distance from your farm do concentrates come from?	production_site_conc	> 200 km	0,0		
16	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	1	1	What percentage of forage (hay, silage, haylage) is refused in the feed space?	perc_feed_remnant	> 10%	0,0		
17	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	1	1	What percentage of dung and urine patches are left ungrazed in your paddock?	grazed_patches	>10%	0,0		
18	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	High-quality forage	1	0	Do you mow in the early plant phenological stage to cut high quality forage (exception HNV and Natura 2000 site)?	cutting_time	NA	n.a.		
19	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	High-quality forage	1	0	Do you include legumes in your mown grasslands?	legume_silage	NA (I am not allowed to reseed or overseed my grasslands)	n.a.		
20	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	1	1	What percentage of your farm has optimal soil fertility (mineral soils index 3/4 P and K and soil pH > 6.3)?	soil_fertility	<70%	50,0		
21	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	1	1	Do you soil test your farm?	soil_testing	No	0,0		
22	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	1	1	What is the soil organic matter	perc_organicmatter	3% or more	100,0		

						content of your permanent grasslands?					
23	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil health	1	1	Do you avoid soil compaction by avoiding grazing in very wet conditions, using low pressure tyres and limited use of heavy machinery?	soil_compaction	Just 1/0 options	0,0		
24	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil health	1	1	Do you use minimum till methods for reseeding?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
25	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil fertiliy	1	0	Do you spread lime when required?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
26	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	Do you spread manure and slurry produced on farm on paddocks that produce forage and crops for your farm?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
27	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	Do you analyse your slurry and manure?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
28	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	How often do your mown grasslands get some organic matter (dung)?	dung_mowingarea	At least every 1-2 years	100,0		
29	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	Do you use low emission slurry and manure spreading to improve nitrogen content?	yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100,0		

30	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Precision technology	1	1	Do you use precision technology (i.e GPS etc.,) to spread chemical fertiliser?	yes_positive_0_100_na	Yes	100,0		
31	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	1	1	When you use fertilisers, do you consider the amount of nitrogen in the soil?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
32	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	1	1	Do you match your nutrient application to the months of plant growth?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
33	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Chemical Nitrogen	1	1	How much chemical nitrogen do you spread on your grazed grasslands?	kg_N_grazingarea	> 200 kg N/ha	0,0		
34	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Chemical Nitrogen	1	1	How much chemical nitrogen do you spread on your mown grasslands?	kg_N_mowingarea	>200 kg N/ha	0,0		
35	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Precision technology	1	1	Do you use any management tools to know when best to apply nutrients?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		

4.2.2 Questions Pillar “Enhancing Diversity”

Nr.	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Weight (default: 1)	Effective Weight (0 for n.a.)	Question	Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	21,3
1	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	1	1	Do you choose multiple pastures species to graze as long as possible in your natural conditions?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
2	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	1	1	Do you use multiple varieties of the same species in your grass seed mixtures (seed grasslands)?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
3	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	1	1	Do you incorporate other species than grass/legumes in your seed grasslands? (eg chicory, plantain...)	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
4	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	1	1	Do you reduce your reliance on chemical fertiliser by incorporating legumes and/or by utilising organic nutrients?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
5	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grassland	1	1	Do you use external farm areas to extend your seasonal grazing areas?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
6	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Do your final products come from different grazing animal species (eg cow, sheep...)?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
7	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Do you practice co grazing with different grazing species? (Co grazing: A	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		

						method of utilizing two or more groups of animals, usually with different nutritional requirements, to graze sequentially on the same land area.)					
8	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Do you use a leader-follower system in grazing? (Leader-follower grazing is where a priority group graze the best grass and the follower group tidy up behind them)	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
9	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Are your animal species/breeds adapted to your local conditions for grazing? (eg. steep; wet; dry; cold,.. etc)	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
10	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Do you have different animal breeds of the same animal species on your farm?	breed_differences	1 breed	0,0		
11	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Do you implement cross-breeding (eg. Holstein with Jersey,..)?	yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100,0		
12	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Grazing animals	1	1	Do you have heritage breeds/local breeds?	yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100,0		
13	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Fodder production	1	1	How many different forage crops do you produce on your farm to maintain production over the year (eg. grass; maize; sorghum; kale,..etc)?	types_crops_forage	≥ 3 types	100,0		

14	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Fodder production	1	0	Do you vary your sowing dates for your forage crops to minimize risks?	sowingdates_crops_forage	No forage crops are sown.	n.a.		
15	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Fodder production	1	0	Do you sow forages that can be harvested in different months across the year ?	sowingdates_crops_forage	No forage crops are sown.	n.a.		
16	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Agroforestry	1	1	Do you include agroforestry on your grasslands? (Agroforestry is a collective name for land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos, etc.) are deliberately used on the same land-management units as agricultural crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence. Agroforestry also includes agro silvo pastoralism).	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
17	Enhancing Diversity	Diversity of production	Agroforestry	1	1	How many trees and shrubs species do you have in your farm?	woody_species	Between 10 and 5 species	75,0		
18	Enhancing Diversity	Marketing	Quality labels	1	1	Are your products sold with quality labels strongly linked to the territory (PDO) ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
19	Enhancing Diversity	Marketing	Retailor network	1	1	Through how many outlets do you sell your products? (e.g., slaughter house; dairy; farm shop; supermarkets etc)	number_retailer	2	50,0		

20	Enhancing Diversity	Marketing	Retailor network	1	1	Can you change your selling channels network easily?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
21	Enhancing Diversity	Marketing	Retailor network	1	1	Do you directly sell your products to your final consumers ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
22	Enhancing Diversity	Income	Income portfolio	1	1	Are you carrying out other economic activities in your farm? (eg: agritourism, agri-camping, hunting ...)	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		

4.2.3 Questions Pillar “Reducing Pollution”

Nr.	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Weight (default: 1)	Effective Weight (0 for n.a.)	Question	Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	0, 0
1	Reducing pollution	Grassland management	Soil cover	1	1	Do you reseed your grasslands taking into account the risk of N leaching and/or erosion?	reseeding_time	Autumn	0,0		
2	Reducing pollution	Grassland management	Soil cover	1	1	Do you adapt nutrient use to soil fertility ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
3	Reducing pollution	Grassland management	Grazing	0,25	0,25	Do you allocate the correct amount of herbage to avoid over or under grazing ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
4	Reducing pollution	Grassland management	Grazing	0,5	0,5	Do you use a paddock to stock animals and offer extra forage/feed for more than a week, e.g. in case of drought? (parking paddock)	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
5	Reducing pollution	Grassland management	Feeding	0,5	0,5	Do you feed high amounts (>3 kg) of concentrate with a high level of crude protein in spring and in autumn (>16 % CP)?	yes_negative_0_100	Yes	0,0		
6	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Infrastructures	1	1	Do you have adequate storage for manure and slurry ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
7	Reducing	Fertilisation	Infrastructures	1	1	Does your slurry storage have a cover ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		

	pollution										
8	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Material	1	1	Do you use a low emission slurry spreading to reduce ammonia emissions ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
9	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Spreading	0,5	0,5	Do you adapt your spreading plan to the spreading risks associated with your soil types ?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
10	Reducing pollution	Fertilisation	Spreading	0,5	0,5	Do you match nutrient application to the months of plant growth?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
11	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	1	1	What percentage of bare ground do you have over winter on your farm ?	perc_bareground	>10%	0,0		
12	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	1	0	Do you use legumes in your crop rotation?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
13	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	1	0	Do you have catch crops to limit bare soil in autumn/winter period?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
14	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	0,5	0	What is the average duration of a crop rotation?	crop_rotation	NA	n.a.		
15	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	0,5	0	Do you incorporate temporary grasslands for 3 years or more in your rotation? (in case of arable cropping)	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		

16	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil cover	1	1	What percentage of your farm is in permanent grassland ?	perc_permanent_grassland	<30%	0,0		
17	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil compaction	0,25	0,25	Do you avoid soil compaction by: avoiding grazing in very wet conditions, using low pressure tires, limited use of heavy machinery?	soil_compaction	1 or 0 option	0,0		
18	Reducing pollution	Soil management	Soil compaction	0,25	0	Do you use minimum till method for reseeding?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
19	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Pesticides use	0,5	0	Do you have a safe-pesticide-use-training course completed?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
20	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Pesticides use	1	0	Do you spray when the weather is windy?	yes_negative_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
21	Reducing pollution	Pest regulation	Biological control	1	1	Do you create habitat (hedgerows, ...) for insects that will help for pest regulation?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
22	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection	Effluents	1	0	Do you include riparian margins next to waterways?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
23	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection	Effluents	1	1	Do you respect the "X m" boundary (buffer zone) when spreading fertiliser/manure/slurry/pesticides near waterways?	yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0,0		

24	Reducing pollution	Waterway protection	Effluents	0,5	0,5	Do you ensure no effluent escapes from your yard? (separate clean water pipes, pond, appropriate storage of silage)	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
----	--------------------	---------------------	-----------	-----	-----	--	--------------------	----	-----	--	--

4.2.4 Questions Pillar “Biodiversity”

Nr .	Pillar	Sub-Pillar	Category	Weight (default : 1)	Effective Weight (for n.a.)	Question	Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	14, 8
1	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Area in biodiversity	1	1	Which percentage of the agriculturally used area of your farm is primarily managed to increase biodiversity?	biodiv_area_pcnt	0	0,0		
2	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Linked habitats	1	1	Are your biodiverse areas connected through landscape elements (e.g. hedgerows, continuous linear structures with woody plants, extensively managed grassland, riparian margins, etc.)?	biodiv_connectedness	Not connected	0,0		
3	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Ponds/wetlands	0,9	0,9	Do you have ponds/wetlands on your farm?	ponds_wetlands	No	0,0		
4	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Rocky outcrops	0,9	0,9	Do you have rocky outcrops/stone	outcrops	No	0,0		

						piles on your farm?					
5	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	0,8	0,8	Choose the most representative plot of temporary grassland on your farm and do this calculation: Plot shape index for sown grassland (having been renewed by sowing) = $\text{perimeter in m} / (2 * (\text{sqr}(3,14 * \text{area in ha})))$	temp_grassland_shape_idx	> 1.7	100,0		
6	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	0,9	0,9	Choose the most representative plot of permanent grassland on your farm and do this calculation: Plot shape index for seminatural grassland (having never been renewed) = $\text{perimeter in m} / (2 * (\text{sqr}(3,14 * \text{area in ha})))$	perm_grassland_shape_idx	> 1.7	100,0		
7	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	0,8	0,8	Choose the most representative plot of crops on your farm and do	cropland_shape_idx	> 1.7	100,0		

						this calculation: Plot shape index for arable crops = perimeter in m / (2*(sqr(3,14*area in ha)))					
8	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	0,6	0,6	What is the size of your average plot of arable crops?	arable_crop_plot_size	There are no arable crops at the farm	0,0		
9	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Landscape structure	0,7	0,7	How many grassland plots over 12 ha?	grassland_plots_greater_12 ha	≥3	0,0		
10	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Woody plants	1	1	What is the percentage of the total agricultural area covered by woody plants (hedgerows: width x length; trees: number of trees x 1.5 m²)?	woody_plants_pcmt	0	0,0		
11	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Woody plants	1	0	Are woody plants arranged in conjunction with each other (e.g. continuous linear structures like hedgerows or fragmented forested patches)?	woody_plants_conjunc	There are no woody plants at the farm	n.a.		

12	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Woody plants	0,7	0	What is the typical width of your hedgerows/woody plant patches?	woody_plants_width	Hedgerows are <1 m wide or no woody plants on farm	n.a.		
13	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Woody plants	1	0	How often do you prune woody plants?	woody_plants_prune	There are no woody plants at the farm	n.a.		
14	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Woody plants	0,8	0	How do you manage your hedgerows?	hedgerows_mngmnt	There are no hedgerows on the farm	n.a.		
15	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Orchards	0,7	0,7	If you have an orchard, what is the density of trees in the orchard?	orchard_density	≥100 trees/ha	0,0		
16	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Protection of natural areas	0,9	0,9	Which is the percentage of SAC (Special Area of Conservation according to the European Union's Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC) on your farm?	sac_pcmt	1.1-4%	50,0		
17	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Riparian margins	1	1	Do you have native vegetation included in your riparian margin?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		

18	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Birds	0,8	0,8	Do you have nest boxes in your recently built barns/sheds to shelter nocturnal birds?	nocturnal_bird_boxes	No	0,0		
19	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Birds	0,8	0,8	Is your barn built in a way in order not to harm/trap birds?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
20	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Connectivity	1	1	Is there a connection between the landscape elements (e.g. hedgerows, continuous linear structures with woody plants, extensively managed grassland, etc.) and your barn?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
21	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Food supply for insects	1	1	Do you have flowering grassland vegetation between February and October on your farm?	flowering_grassland	<10% of the total grassland area	0,0		
22	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Control of invasive species	0,9	0	How do you control invasive species (animals/plants with rapidly	invasive species	There are no invasive species to be	n.a.		

						increasing abundance) on your farm?		controlled at my farm			
23	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	0,9	0,9	How often do you mow your meadows beginning from the centre?	always_sometimes_never	Never	0,0		
24	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	0,9	0,9	Is the mowing period tailored to protect ground nesting birds?	always_sometimes_never	Never	0,0		
25	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	0,9	0,9	Which percentage of grassland at your farm incorporates a combination of utilisation practices (grazing, mowing)?	utilisation_combination	In 0-50% of the surface mowing and grazing are combined	0,0		
26	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	0,8	0,8	Are grazing refusals (urine/dung) patches being mown more than once per year?	yes_negative_0_100	Yes	0,0		
27	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Grassland management	0,9	0,9	How much total nitrogen (chemical fertilisers and manures) is applied to extensive grasslands?	nitrogen	>100 kg N/ha	0,0		

28	Biodiversity	Habitat management	Livestock management	0,8	0,8	Is the livestock chemically treated against insects or nematodes in the field?	yes_negative_0_100	Yes	0,0		
----	--------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----	-----	--	--------------------	-----	-----	--	--

4.2.5 Questions Pillar “Animal Welfare”

Nr.	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Weight (default: 1)	Effective Weight (0 for n.a.)	Question	Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	10,4
1	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Paths and roads quality	0,75	0,75	What is the daily distance that animals walk to the paddock?	walkdistance_dairycow	Less than 1 km	100,0		
2	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Paths and roads quality	1	1	What proportion of animals are lame each year?	perc_lame_animals	>15%	0,0		
3	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Paths and roads quality	0,5	0,5	Do your roadways have uneven surfaces?	no_positive_0_100	Yes	0,0		
4	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Paths and roads quality	0,5	0,5	Are your roadways maintained yearly?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
5	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Access to shade/shelter	1	1	In cases of sun, do grazing animals have access to shade/shelter?	shade_access	Never	0,0		
6	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Housing	1	0	Do adult animals have access to cubicles (one cubicle per cow) or loose housing (4m ² /cow) ?	cubicles_loosehousing	NA	n.a.		
7	Animal Welfare	Infrastructure	Water access and quality	1	1	Do animals have access to fresh clean water at all times (including grazing) ?	access_fresh_water	Access to fresh water sometimes	33,0		
8	Animal Welfare	Nutrition	Balanced ration	1	0	Do you have digestive or	yes_negative_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		

						metabolic problems during the transition period of cows?					
9	Animal Welfare	Nutrition	Balanced ration	0,5	0,5	Do you adapt your supplements to the forage quality?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
10	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	1	1	Is your treatment of animals systematic against parasites or based on analyses (faeces and others)?	treatment_animal	Systematic	0,0		
11	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	1	1	How many times per year do you trim hooves?	hoove_trimming	Less than once per year	0,0		
12	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	1	1	What is the occurrence mastitis in your herd or flock?	frequence_mastitis	>10%	0,0		
13	Animal Welfare	Health management	Profilaxy	1	1	What is the mortality rate of your young stock (from 4 months to 12 months)?	mort_rate	>10%	0,0		
14	Animal Welfare	Health management	Veterinary services	1	1	When do you call the vet for sick/injured animals that need veterinary attention?	call_vet	Later than 6 hours after visual detection	0,0		
15	Animal Welfare	Health management	Veterinary services	1	1	How often do you visually check grazing animals but cows (suckler cows,	check_interval	Less than every two days	0,0		

						other beef cattle, sheep, goats)					
16	Animal Welfare	Animal behavior and welfare	Grazing management	1	1	Do you let your animals graze under wet (saturated/muddy soil) conditions?	no_positive_0_100	Yes	0,0		
17	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	1	1	Is colostrum ingested within 3 hours after birth?	colostrum_3h	No, colostrum feeding within 3 hours is not systematically checked	0,0		
18	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	1	1	Is the colostrum of dairy cows of good quality?	colostrum_quality	No measurement or bad quality according to the measurements	0,0		
19	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	1	1	Do calves/lambs/kids before weaning share the same indoor airspace as the older animals?	calves_space	Yes, but not more than 30 animals incl. young stock and older cattle share the same air space	50,0		
20	Animal Welfare	Calf welfare and health	Health management	1	0	How much space is allocated per calf before weaning?	housing_calves	NA	n.a.		

4.2.6 Radar graph summarising results of each pillar

Pillar	Nr. Questions	Eval value
Reducing Inputs	35	27,4
Enhancing Diversity	22	21,3
Reducing Pollution	24	0,0
Biodiversity	28	14,8
Animal Welfare	20	10,4

Sub-pillars	
Maximising herbage utilisation	14
Reducing feed inputs	5
Soil management	6
Optimising chemical fertilisation	6
Optimising organic nutrients on farm	4
Diversity of production	17
Marketing	4
Income	1
Grassland management	5
Fertilisation	5
Soil management	8
Pest regulation	3
Waterway protection	3
Habitat management	28
Infrastructure	7
Nutrition	2
Health management	6
Animal behavior and welfare	1
Calf welfare and health	4

4.2.7 Dropdown values

Full_Value_Name	Field type	Select Value	Eval Value (%)
biodiv_area_pcmt_>10%	biodiv_area_pcmt	>10%	100
biodiv_area_pcmt_9.1-10%	biodiv_area_pcmt	9.1-10%	75
biodiv_area_pcmt_5.1-9%	biodiv_area_pcmt	5.1-9%	50
biodiv_area_pcmt_0.1-5%	biodiv_area_pcmt	0.1-5%	10
biodiv_area_pcmt_0	biodiv_area_pcmt	0%	0
biodiv_connectedness_Con nected to 2 other areas	biodiv_connectedness	Connected to 2 other areas	100
biodiv_connectedness_Con nected to 1 other area	biodiv_connectedness	Connected to 1 other area	50
biodiv_connectedness_Not connected	biodiv_connectedness	Not connected	0
ponds_wetlands_Yes, they are carefully managed and monitored	ponds_wetlands	Yes, they are carefully managed and monitored	100
ponds_wetlands_Yes, but no management or monitoring is applied	ponds_wetlands	Yes, but no management or monitoring is applied	66
ponds_wetlands_No	ponds_wetlands	No	0
outcrops_Yes, they are protected from human and grazing pressure (e.g. fenced)	outcrops	Yes, they are protected from human and grazing pressure (e.g. fenced)	100
outcrops_Yes, but they are not protected	outcrops	Yes, but they are not protected	66
outcrops_No	outcrops	No	0
temp_grassland_shape_idx > 1.7	temp_grassland_shape_idx	> 1.7	100
temp_grassland_shape_idx _1.1-1.7	temp_grassland_shape_idx	1.1-1.7	50
temp_grassland_shape_idx _<1.1	temp_grassland_shape_idx	<1.1	0
temp_grassland_shape_idx _There is no temporary grassland at the farm	temp_grassland_shape_idx	There is no temporary grassland at the farm	0
perm_grassland_shape_idx > 1.7	perm_grassland_shape_idx	> 1.7	100
perm_grassland_shape_idx _1.1-1.7	perm_grassland_shape_idx	1.1-1.7	50
perm_grassland_shape_idx _<1.1	perm_grassland_shape_idx	<1.1	0
perm_grassland_shape_idx _There is no permanent grassland at the farm	perm_grassland_shape_idx	There is no permanent grassland at the farm	0
cropland_shape_idx_> 1.7	cropland_shape_idx	> 1.7	100
cropland_shape_idx_1.1-1.7	cropland_shape_idx	1.1-1.7	50
cropland_shape_idx_<1.1	cropland_shape_idx	<1.1	0

cropland_shape_idx_There is no arable crops at the farm	cropland_shape_idx	There is no arable crops at the farm	0
arable_crop_plot_size_ < 5 ha	arable_crop_plot_size	< 5 ha	100
arable_crop_plot_size_5-10 ha	arable_crop_plot_size	5-10 ha	50
arable_crop_plot_size_ > 10 ha	arable_crop_plot_size	> 10 ha	0
arable_crop_plot_size_There are no arable crops at the farm	arable_crop_plot_size	There are no arable crops at the farm	0
grassland_plots_greater_12 ha_0	grassland_plots_greater_12 ha	0	100
grassland_plots_greater_12 ha_1-2	grassland_plots_greater_12 ha	1-2	50
grassland_plots_greater_12 ha_≥3	grassland_plots_greater_12 ha	≥3	0
woody_plants_pcmt_ >4%	woody_plants_pcmt	>4%	100
woody_plants_pcmt_2.1-4%	woody_plants_pcmt	2.1-4%	75
woody_plants_pcmt_0.1-2%	woody_plants_pcmt	0.1-2%	50
woody_plants_pcmt_0	woody_plants_pcmt	0%	0
woody_plants_conjunc_Continuous linear structures	woody_plants_conjunc	Continuous linear structures	100
woody_plants_conjunc_Forested patches	woody_plants_conjunc	Forested patches	85
woody_plants_conjunc_Woody plant patches exist but are not interconnected	woody_plants_conjunc	Woody plant patches exist but are not interconnected	66
woody_plants_conjunc_Woody plants are integrated as single elements	woody_plants_conjunc	Woody plants are integrated as single elements	50
woody_plants_conjunc_There are no woody plants at the farm	woody_plants_conjunc	There are no woody plants at the farm	n.a.
woody_plants_width_ >3 m wide hedgerows/patches	woody_plants_width	>3 m wide hedgerows/patches	100
woody_plants_width_2.1-3 m wide hedgerows/patches	woody_plants_width	2.1-3 m wide hedgerows/patches	66
woody_plants_width_1-2 m wide hedgerows/patches	woody_plants_width	1-2 m wide hedgerows/patches	33
woody_plants_width_Hedgerows are <1 m wide or no woody plants on farm	woody_plants_width	Hedgerows are <1 m wide or no woody plants on farm	n.a.
woody_plants_prune_Following support scheme management plan	woody_plants_prune	Following support scheme management plan	100
woody_plants_prune_Hedgerows are pruned every 5 years or longer	woody_plants_prune	Hedgerows are pruned every 5 years or longer	100
woody_plants_prune_Hedgerows are pruned every 3-5 years	woody_plants_prune	Hedgerows are pruned every 3-5 years	75

woody_plants_prune_Hedgerows are pruned every 2 years	woody_plants_prune	Hedgerows are pruned every 2 years	50
woody_plants_prune_Hedgerows are pruned yearly	woody_plants_prune	Hedgerows are pruned yearly	33
woody_plants_prune_There are no woody plants at the farm	woody_plants_prune	There are no woody plants at the farm	n.a.
hedgerows_mngmnt_Only part of the hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is not mown	hedgerows_mngmnt	Only part of the hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is not mown	100
hedgerows_mngmnt_Only part of the hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is mown	hedgerows_mngmnt	Only part of the hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is mown	75
hedgerows_mngmnt_All hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is not mown	hedgerows_mngmnt	All hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is not mown	50
hedgerows_mngmnt_All hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is mown	hedgerows_mngmnt	All hedgerows are pruned at once, the vegetation close to the hedgerows is mown	33
hedgerows_mngmnt_There are no hedgerows on the farm	hedgerows_mngmnt	There are no hedgerows on the farm	n.a.
orchard_density_<100 trees/ha	orchard_density	<100 trees/ha	100
orchard_density_≥100 trees/ha	orchard_density	≥100 trees/ha	0
orchard_density_There are no orchards at the farm	orchard_density	There are no orchards at the farm	n.a.
sac_pcmt_>10%	sac_pcmt	>10%	100
sac_pcmt_4.1-10%	sac_pcmt	4.1-10%	75
sac_pcmt_1.1-4%	sac_pcmt	1.1-4%	50
sac_pcmt_0-1%	sac_pcmt	0-1%	25
sac_pcmt_0	sac_pcmt	0%	0
yes_positive_0_100_Yes	yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100
yes_positive_0_100_No	yes_positive_0_100	No	0
nocturnal_bird_boxes_Yes	nocturnal_bird_boxes	Yes	100
nocturnal_bird_boxes_No, but I have no recently built barn	nocturnal_bird_boxes	No, but I have no recently built barn	100
nocturnal_bird_boxes_No	nocturnal_bird_boxes	No	0
flowering_grassland_>20% of the total grassland area	flowering_grassland	>20% of the total grassland area	100

flowering_grassland_10-20% of the total grassland area	flowering_grassland	10-20% of the total grassland area	50
flowering_grassland_<10% of the total grassland area	flowering_grassland	<10% of the total grassland area	0
invasive species_Naturally (e.g. favouring the activity of natural predators, changing the fertilisation regime, etc.)	invasive species	Naturally (e.g. favouring the activity of natural predators, changing the fertilisation regime, etc.)	100
invasive species_Mechanically	invasive species	Mechanically	50
invasive species_Chemically	invasive species	Chemically	0
invasive species_There are no invasive species to be controlled at my farm	invasive species	There are no invasive species to be controlled at my farm	n.a.
always_sometimes_never_Always	always_sometimes_never	Always	100
always_sometimes_never_Sometimes	always_sometimes_never	Sometimes	50
always_sometimes_never_Never	always_sometimes_never	Never	0
utilisation_combination_In >50% of the surface mowing and grazing are combined	utilisation_combination	In >50% of the surface mowing and grazing are combined	100
utilisation_combination_In 0-50% of the surface mowing and grazing are combined	utilisation_combination	In 0-50% of the surface mowing and grazing are combined	0
yes_negative_0_100_Yes	yes_negative_0_100	Yes	0
yes_negative_0_100_No	yes_negative_0_100	No	100
nitrogen_0-40 kg N/ha	nitrogen	0-40 kg N/ha	100
nitrogen_41-100 kg N/ha	nitrogen	41-100 kg N/ha	30
nitrogen_>100 kg N/ha	nitrogen	>100 kg N/ha	0
legumes_sow_Yes	legumes_sow	Yes	100
legumes_sow_No	legumes_sow	No	0
legumes_sow_NA	legumes_sow	NA	n.a.
perc_legumes_> 30%	perc_legumes	> 30%	100
perc_legumes_20-30%	perc_legumes	20-30%	75
perc_legumes_10-20%	perc_legumes	10-20%	50
perc_legumes_<10%	perc_legumes	<10%	25
perc_farmforage_All (100%)	perc_farmforage	All (100%)	100
perc_farmforage_> 70%	perc_farmforage	> 70%	66
perc_farmforage_< 70%	perc_farmforage	< 70%	33
yes_positive_0_100_na_Yes	yes_positive_0_100_na	Yes	100

yes_positive_0_100_na_No	yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0
yes_positive_0_100_na_NA	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.
grazing_days_> 80%	grazing_days	> 80%	100
grazing_days_60-80%	grazing_days	60-80%	66
grazing_days_40-60%	grazing_days	40-60%	33
grazing_days_< 40%	grazing_days	< 40%	0
yes_positive_50_100_Yes	yes_positive_50_100	Yes	50
yes_positive_50_100_No	yes_positive_50_100	No	100
perc_springdiet_0 - 20%	perc_springdiet	0 - 20%	100
perc_springdiet_> 20%	perc_springdiet	> 20%	0
kg_concentrate_spring_0 kg/animal	kg_concentrate_spring	0 kg/animal	100
kg_concentrate_spring_0 - 3 kg/cow; 0-0,5 kg /small ruminants	kg_concentrate_spring	0 - 3 kg/cow; 0-0,5 kg /small ruminants	75
kg_concentrate_spring_>3 kg/cow; > 0,5 kg /small ruminants	kg_concentrate_spring	>3 kg/cow; > 0,5 kg /small ruminants	25
perc_XP_< 15%	perc_XP	< 15%	100
perc_XP_> 15%	perc_XP	> 15%	0
hours_grazing_> 12 hours	hours_grazing	> 12 hours	100
hours_grazing_< 12 hours	hours_grazing	< 12 hours	50
hours_grazing_No grazing	hours_grazing	No grazing	0
kg_concentrate_summer_0 kg/animal	kg_concentrate_summer	0 kg/animal	100
kg_concentrate_summer_0 - 3 kg/cow; 0-0,5 kg /small ruminants	kg_concentrate_summer	0 - 3 kg/cow; 0-0,5 kg /small ruminants	75
kg_concentrate_summer_> 3 kg/cow; > 0,5 kg /small ruminants	kg_concentrate_summer	>3 kg/cow; > 0,5 kg /small ruminants	25
autumn_grazing_> 6 hours	autumn_grazing	> 6 hours	100
autumn_grazing_< 6 hours	autumn_grazing	< 6 hours	50
autumn_grazing_Not on pasture	autumn_grazing	Not on pasture	0
production_site_conc_Produced on farm	production_site_conc	Produced on farm	100
production_site_conc_<50 km from the farm	production_site_conc	<50 km from the farm	75
production_site_conc_50 - 200 km	production_site_conc	50 - 200 km	25
production_site_conc_> 200 km	production_site_conc	> 200 km	0
perc_feed_remnant_< 10%	perc_feed_remnant	< 10%	100
perc_feed_remnant_> 10%	perc_feed_remnant	> 10%	0
grazed_patches_< 5%	grazed_patches	< 5%	75

grazed_patches_5-10%	grazed_patches	5-10%	50
grazed_patches_>10%	grazed_patches	>10%	0
cutting_time_Yes	cutting_time	Yes	100
cutting_time_No	cutting_time	No	0
cutting_time_NA	cutting_time	NA	n.a.
legume_silage_Yes	legume_silage	Yes	100
legume_silage_No	legume_silage	No	0
legume_silage_NA (I am not allowed to reseed or overseed my grasslands)	legume_silage	NA (I am not allowed to reseed or overseed my grasslands)	n.a.
soil_fertility_>90%	soil_fertility	>90%	100
soil_fertility_70-90%	soil_fertility	70-90%	75
soil_fertility_<70%	soil_fertility	<70%	50
soil_testing_Yes	soil_testing	Yes	100
soil_testing_No	soil_testing	No	0
perc_organicmatter_3% or more	perc_organicmatter	3% or more	100
perc_organicmatter_less than 3%	perc_organicmatter	less than 3%	0
soil_compaction_All 3 options	soil_compaction	All 3 options	100
soil_compaction_Only 2 options	soil_compaction	Only 2 options	50
soil_compaction_Just 1/0 options	soil_compaction	Just 1/0 options	0
yes_positive_0_100_Yes	yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100
yes_positive_0_100_No	yes_positive_0_100	No	0
kg_N_grazingarea_<80 kg N/ha	kg_N_grazingarea	<80 kg N/ha	100
kg_N_grazingarea_80 -150 kg N/ha	kg_N_grazingarea	80 -150 kg N/ha	75
kg_N_grazingarea_150-200 kg N/ha	kg_N_grazingarea	150-200 kg N/ha	25
kg_N_grazingarea_> 200 kg N/ha	kg_N_grazingarea	> 200 kg N/ha	0
kg_N_mowingarea_<100 kg N/ha	kg_N_mowingarea	<100 kg N/ha	100
kg_N_mowingarea_100-200 kg N/ha	kg_N_mowingarea	100-200 kg N/ha	50
kg_N_mowingarea_>200 kg N/ha	kg_N_mowingarea	>200 kg N/ha	0
dung_mowingarea_At least every 1-2 years	dung_mowingarea	At least every 1-2 years	100
dung_mowingarea_3 or more years	dung_mowingarea	3 or more years	0
reseeding_time_Late winter/early spring	reseeding_time	Late winter/early spring	100
reseeding_time_Autumn	reseeding_time	Autumn	0

reseeding_time_NA	reseeding_time	NA	n.a.
perc_bareground_0	perc_bareground	0%	100
perc_bareground_1-5%	perc_bareground	1-5%	66
perc_bareground_6-10%	perc_bareground	6-10%	33
perc_bareground_>10%	perc_bareground	>10%	0
crop_rotation_≤ 3 years	crop_rotation	≤ 3 years	0
crop_rotation_4-7 years	crop_rotation	4-7 years	50
crop_rotation_≥ 8 years	crop_rotation	≥ 8 years	100
crop_rotation_NA	crop_rotation	NA	n.a.
perc_permanent_grassland_> 70%	perc_permanent_grassland	> 70%	100
perc_permanent_grassland_50-70%	perc_permanent_grassland	50-70%	66
perc_permanent_grassland_30-49%	perc_permanent_grassland	30-49%	33
perc_permanent_grassland_<30%	perc_permanent_grassland	<30%	0
soil_compaction_3 options	soil_compaction	3 options	100
soil_compaction_2 options	soil_compaction	2 options	50
soil_compaction_1 or 0 option	soil_compaction	1 or 0 option	0
yes_negative_0_100_na_Yes	yes_negative_0_100_na	Yes	0
yes_negative_0_100_na_No	yes_negative_0_100_na	No	100
yes_negative_0_100_na_NA	yes_negative_0_100_na	NA	n.a.
treatment_animal_Analyses	treatment_animal	Analyses	100
treatment_animal_Systematic	treatment_animal	Systematic	0
hoove_trimming_At least once per year	hoove_trimming	At least once per year	100
hoove_trimming_Less than once per year	hoove_trimming	Less than once per year	0
frequence_mastitis_<5%	frequence_mastitis	<5%	100
frequence_mastitis_5-10%	frequence_mastitis	5-10%	50
frequence_mastitis_>10%	frequence_mastitis	>10%	0
mort_rate_≤5%	mort_rate	≤5%	100
mort_rate_6-10%	mort_rate	6-10%	50
mort_rate_>10%	mort_rate	>10%	0
call_vet_Immediately upon visual detection	call_vet	Immediately upon visual detection	100
call_vet_Within 6 hours after visual detection	call_vet	Within 6 hours after visual detection	50
call_vet_Later than 6 hours after visual detection	call_vet	Later than 6 hours after visual detection	0
check_interval_At least once a day	check_interval	At least once a day	100

check_interval_Once every two days	check_interval	Once every two days	50
check_interval_Less than every two days	check_interval	Less than every two days	0
no_positive_0_100_Yes	no_positive_0_100	Yes	0
no_positive_0_100_No	no_positive_0_100	No	100
colostrum_3h_Yes	colostrum_3h	Yes	100
colostrum_3h_No, colostrum feeding within 3 hours is not systematically checked	colostrum_3h	No, colostrum feeding within 3 hours is not systematically checked	0
colostrum_quality_Yes, >22% on the brix refractometer	colostrum_quality	Yes, >22% on the brix refractometer	100
colostrum_quality_Yes, checked with another kind of measurement	colostrum_quality	Yes, checked with another kind of measurement	50
colostrum_quality_No measurement or bad quality according to the measurements	colostrum_quality	No measurement or bad quality according to the measurements	0
calves_space_Yes, more than 30 animals incl. young stock and older cattle share the same air space	calves_space	Yes, more than 30 animals incl. young stock and older cattle share the same air space	0
calves_space_Yes, but not more than 30 animals incl. young stock and older cattle share the same air space	calves_space	Yes, but not more than 30 animals incl. young stock and older cattle share the same air space	50
calves_space_No, young stock is kept up to 30 animals together and they do not share the same air space with older cattle	calves_space	No, young stock is kept up to 30 animals together and they do not share the same air space with older cattle	100
housing_calves_2 m ² or more	housing_calves	2 m ² or more	100
housing_calves_1,5 - 2 m ²	housing_calves	1,5 - 2 m ²	50
housing_calves_<1,5 m	housing_calves	<1,5 m	0
housing_calves_NA	housing_calves	NA	n.a.
walkdistance_dairycow_Less than 1 km	walkdistance_dairycow	Less than 1 km	100
walkdistance_dairycow_1-2 km	walkdistance_dairycow	1-2 km	50
walkdistance_dairycow_> 2 km	walkdistance_dairycow	> 2 km	0
perc_lame_animals_< 5%	perc_lame_animals	< 5%	100
perc_lame_animals_5-15%	perc_lame_animals	5-15%	50
perc_lame_animals_>15%	perc_lame_animals	>15%	0
no_positive_0_100_No	no_positive_0_100	No	100
no_positive_0_100_Yes	no_positive_0_100	Yes	0

shade_access_Always	shade_access	Always	100
shade_access_Often	shade_access	Often	66
shade_access_Sometimes	shade_access	Sometimes	33
shade_access_Never	shade_access	Never	0
cubicles_loosehousing_Always	cubicles_loosehousing	Always	100
cubicles_loosehousing_Often	cubicles_loosehousing	Often	66
cubicles_loosehousing_Sometimes	cubicles_loosehousing	Sometimes	33
cubicles_loosehousing_Never	cubicles_loosehousing	Never	0
cubicles_loosehousing_NA	cubicles_loosehousing	NA	n.a.
access_fresh_water_Access to fresh clean water at all times	access_fresh_water	Access to fresh clean water at all times	100
access_fresh_water_Access to fresh water at all times	access_fresh_water	Access to fresh water at all times	66
access_fresh_water_Access to fresh water sometimes	access_fresh_water	Access to fresh water sometimes	33
access_fresh_water_No access to water while grazing	access_fresh_water	No access to water while grazing	0
breed_differences_≥ 2 breeds	breed_differences	≥ 2 breeds	100
breed_differences_1 breed	breed_differences	1 breed	0
types_crops_forage_≥ 3 types	types_crops_forage	≥ 3 types	100
types_crops_forage_2 types	types_crops_forage	2 types	50
types_crops_forage_1 type	types_crops_forage	1 type	0
woody_species_≥ 10 species	woody_species	≥ 10 species	100
woody_species_Between 10 and 5 species	woody_species	Between 10 and 5 species	75
woody_species_Between 5 and 3 species	woody_species	Between 5 and 3 species	25
woody_species_Less than 3 species	woody_species	Less than 3 species	0
number_retailer_3 or more	number_retailer	3 or more	100
number_retailer_2	number_retailer	2	50
number_retailer_1	number_retailer	1	0
sowingdates_crops_forage_Yes	sowingdates_crops_forage	Yes	100
sowingdates_crops_forage_No	sowingdates_crops_forage	No	0
sowingdates_crops_forage_No forage crops are sown.	sowingdates_crops_forage	No forage crops are sown.	n.a.

Nr.	Pillar	Sub-pillar	Category	Weight (default: 1)	Effective Weight (0 for n.a.)	Question	Field type	Field value	Eval/Use value (%)	Eval Result (%):	27,4
1	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	1	1	Do you have legumes in your grasslands?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
2	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	1	1	Do you put legumes in your grasslands available for sow?	yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0,0		
3	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Legumes	1	1	What is the maximum proportion of legumes in you pastures throughout the year?	perc_legumes	<10%	25,0		
4	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Sufficient forage production	1	1	What percentage of forage used is produced on your farm in the last three years?	perc_farmforage	All (100%)	100,0		
5	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Grassland Management	1	1	If you mow your grasslands, is your post mowing height for silage/hay between 6 - 8 cm ?	yes_positive_0_100_na	No	0,0		
6	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Grassland Management	1	1	What is the proportion from the optimal grazing period that your animals spend grazing a year?	grazing_days	< 40%	0,0		
7	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	0	Do you try to graze as early as possible in spring?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
8	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	When animals are grazing in the spring are they fed additional forage (hay, silage, haylage, maize silage etc)?	yes_positive_50_100	Yes	50,0		
9	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	If animals are given additional forage in the best grazing period during a year what % of their diet is it?	perc_springdiet	> 20%	0,0		
10	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	During the best yearly grazing period, how much concentrate do you feed a day to a mother animal?	kg_concentrate_spring	>3 kg/cow; > 0,5 kg /small ruminants	25,0		
11	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Spring grazing	1	1	If you do feed concentrate during the best yearly grazing period what crude protein percentage is it?	perc_XP	< 15%	100,0		

12	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Summer grazing	1	1	During summer, how much of the day are animals on pastures?	hours_grazing	No grazing	0,0		
13	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Summer grazing	1	1	During summer, how much concentrate do you feed a day to a mother animal?	kg_concentrate_summer	0 kg/animal	100,0		
14	Reducing inputs	Maximising herbage utilisation	Autumn grazing	1	1	In autumn, how much of the day are animals on pastures?	autumn_grazing	Not on pasture	0,0		
15	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	1	1	What distance from your farm do concentrates come from?	production_site_conc	> 200 km	0,0		
16	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	1	1	What percentage of forage (hay, silage, haylage) is refused in the feed space?	perc_feed_remnant	> 10%	0,0		
17	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	Reducing waste	1	1	What percentage of dung and urine patches are left ungrazed in your paddock?	grazed_patches	>10%	0,0		
18	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	High-quality forage	1	0	Do you mow in the early plant phenological stage to cut high quality forage (exception HNV and Natura 2000 site)?	cutting_time	NA	n.a.		
19	Reducing inputs	Reducing feed inputs	High-quality forage	1	0	Do you include legumes in your mown grasslands?	legume_silage	NA (I am not allowed to reseed or overseed my grasslands)	n.a.		
20	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	1	1	What percentage of your farm has optimal soil fertility (mineral soils index 3/4 P and K and soil pH > 6.3)?	soil_fertility	<70%	50,0		
21	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	1	1	Do you soil test your farm?	soil_testing	No	0,0		
22	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Optimal soil fertility	1	1	What is the soil organic matter content of your permanent grasslands?	perc_organicmatter	3% or more	100,0		

23	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil health	1	1	Do you avoid soil compaction by avoiding grazing in very wet conditions, using low pressure tyres and limited use of heavy machinery?	soil_compaction	Just 1/0 options	0,0		
24	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil health	1	1	Do you use minimum till methods for reseeding?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
25	Reducing inputs	Soil management	Soil fertility	1	0	Do you spread lime when required?	yes_positive_0_100_na	NA	n.a.		
26	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	Do you spread manure and slurry produced on farm on paddocks that produce forage and crops for your farm?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
27	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	Do you analyse your slurry and manure?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
28	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	How often do your mown grasslands get some organic matter (dung)?	dung_mowingarea	At least every 1-2 years	100,0		
29	Reducing inputs	Optimising organic nutrients on farm	Slurry and manure management	1	1	Do you use low emission slurry and manure spreading to improve nitrogen content?	yes_positive_0_100	Yes	100,0		
30	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Precision technology	1	1	Do you use precision technology (i.e GPS etc..) to spread chemical fertiliser?	yes_positive_0_100_na	Yes	100,0		
31	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	1	1	When you use fertilisers, do you consider the amount of nitrogen in the soil?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		
32	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Nitrogen plan	1	1	Do you match your nutrient application to the months of plant growth?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		

33	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Chemical Nitrogen	1	1	How much chemical nitrogen do you spread on your grazed grasslands?	kg_N_grazingarea	> 200 kg N/ha	0,0		
34	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Chemical Nitrogen	1	1	How much chemical nitrogen do you spread on your mown grasslands?	kg_N_mowingarea	>200 kg N/ha	0,0		
35	Reducing inputs	Optimising fertilisation	Precision technology	1	1	Do you use any management tools to know when best to apply nutrients?	yes_positive_0_100	No	0,0		

Consortium:

Contact:

- Website** www.grazing4agroecology.eu
- f** <https://www.facebook.com/Grazing4AgroEcology/>
- t** https://twitter.com/HEurope_G4AE
- in** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/89048577/admin/>
- ▶** <https://www.youtube.com/@Grazing4AgroEcology>